

Financial Sustainability of Community Managed Water Supply Projects in Developing Countries: A Systematic Literature Review

Bidya Nath Bhattarai^{1*}, Pakorn Pasitsuparoad¹, Saroj Gyawali¹, Hari Prasad Ghimire², Hari Prashad Joshi²,

¹Faculty of Technology and Environment, Prince of Songkla University, Phuket, 83120, Thailand

²Everest Centre for Research and Development Partners, Kathmandu Nepal

Corresponding e-mail: bidya37@gmail.com* pakom.p@phuket.psu.ac.th

Abstract – *The aim of this research was to evaluating the sustainability of community water supply systems in the developing countries where 2.2 billion people have no sustainable access to water. While water scarcity causes health deteriorations, economic losses and resource-driven violence. A search was conducted on Scopus using words like 'financial sustainability,' 'Community-managed drinking water supply,' 'Developing countries,' for articles from the years 2000 to 2023. Fields discussed included operations, financial reporting, audit outcomes and community engagement. Sources of funding recognized included fees from user charges, grants from government and international collaboration. Two major sources lay down as imperative to the success of the efforts: community support and government support. Limitations with regard to the chosen methods consisted of issues such as sample representativeness or data collection techniques. It will be advisable to extend this study with cross-country comparison for evaluating the long-term financial viability of the SNGs.*

Keywords: *Financial Sustainability, Community Involvement, Water Supply Projects, Developing Countries, Cost Recovery Mechanisms, Nepal, Asia, "SLR"*

I. Introduction

Access to clean water remains a significant challenge in developing countries, as a substantial number of the population lacks reliable access to safe water supplies. Progress toward universal access to clean water is slowed by rapid population growth, insufficient investment in infrastructure, challenges in developing local water resources, and inefficiencies within institutions responsible for water management in both urban and rural areas. [1] According to the World Health Organization [WHO], Safely managed drinking water services are still dismal, with more than 2 billion people lacking its services worldwide, most of whom reside in the developing world [2]. The lack of access poses serious issues because water is important for drinking, cooking, and washing. The lack of potable drinking water results in waterborne diseases such as frequent incidences of cholera, dysentery, and typhoid fever which extremely affect vulnerable groups of society, especially children and the elderly [3]. Hydro-social dynamics of exclusion and water insecurity experienced by Dalits in peri-urban areas of the Kathmandu Valley, highlighting ongoing but evolving patterns of inequality and marginalization in access to water.[4] Du Plessis and du Plessis [2019] explore the present and future challenges related to water scarcity and stress, focusing on global water availability, quality, and the associated risks, with a specific emphasis on South

Africa.[5]

Water pollution severely threatens global water security, as contamination reduces the availability of clean water and significantly raises treatment costs. [6] The relationship between water supply and health, emphasizes that inadequate and unsafe water supply significantly contributes to global health burdens, particularly through waterborne diseases, highlighting the need for improved water quality and access to reduce preventable health issues. [7] [8] Furthermore number of hours spent on water collection and the distances covered, commonly by women and children, reduce opportunities for education and employment, thus continually generating poverty [9]. Besides, inadequate water supply may result in water-related conflicts which may increase the risks to the stability of a particular community and or region [10]. Good practices in realizing the rights to water and sanitation, emphasize participatory approaches, accountability, and non-discrimination to ensure equitable access to water and sanitation, particularly for marginalized communities, while promoting sustainable management and governance of resources.[11] Effective water governance, emphasizes the importance of community participation in decision-making processes to ensure equitable and sustainable water resource management across diverse global contexts. [12]

Participation by the community in water supply management has several advantages that benefit the success and sustainability of these projects. Firstly, it enriches accountability and transparency by people's

participation in the decision-making processes and observing the proper use of the funds and resources as well as an overview [13].

Some empirical evidence that supports the idea of community-managed water supply projects concerns the following cases. In India, the Swajal Project in the state of Uttar Pradesh enabled the rural communities to develop and manage their water supply systems led to changes in the rural water supply making them accessible and healthier for the communities [17]. Likewise in Kenya, the experience of the 'Maji ni Uhai' intervention showed that full community management is possible and yields impressive results in terms of both water and water-borne illness accessibility through the management of water kiosks [18]. Another example worthy of mention is Bolivia's Basic Sanitation Programme which allowed rural communities to plan, construct, and manage water supplies & sanitation systems leading to safe & sustainable water services [19]. Collectively, these case studies demonstrate the ability of community-based interventions to provide scalable solutions for the extended provision of water services concerning the rights, demographics, and circumstances of constituent communities.

In the case of community-managed water supply projects, financial sustainability must be understood as the capacity of these projects to meet operating and maintenance costs, loan and or debt repayments, and investment in future improvements using funds other than those that come from grants in aid. Sustainability can be improved through advancements in water management, and energy efficiency, underscoring the vital importance of cross-disciplinary collaboration to effectively tackle the environmental challenges confronting our planet. [19] Water, sanitation, and hygiene [WASH] are critical to addressing rural poverty, stressing the importance of sector monitoring and the use of aggregated indicators to measure progress and improve decision-making in poverty-stricken areas. [21]

The NGOs are often known to support government initiatives by offering essential technical support, funds, and capacity enhancement, particularly at the grassroots level. Among the NGOs, involved in water resources management are Water Aid and the International Water Management Institute which supports the monitoring and implementation of sustainable community projects and water rights of the people [22] [23]. Regardless of these efforts, meeting sustainable water supply is a significant challenge, and requires innovative approaches for durable and effective solutions of affected communities.

The study has explained that community-managed water supply projects face several financial risks that compromise the sustainability of the projects in developing countries. The challenges are; first, there is the question of arriving at the correct user fees that can be charged to the community and provide all the operational costs [24]. Besides, such projects may experience fluctuating cash flows because the water demand may be

seasonal, as are the compliance of payments. Digestibility: Lack of adequate access to banking services and credit can also be a reason for the inability to source funds needed for repairs and expansions [25]. In addition, communities have poor financial management skills which can cause poor planning and poor resource management of sustainability issues.

The most recent research on the financial sustainability of community-managed water delivery programs shows a lot of information and numerous incongruent conclusions. Many empirical sources note that financial sustainability is essential for the continuousness of water supply interventions in developing states [27],[28]. For instance, evidence provided by [29] revealed that non-sustainable projects are incapable of securing financial support thus they are unable to maintain the required operations and services which leads to the failure of a project translating to abandonment and community marginalization. Researchers use specific research methods in these studies, including econometric techniques, financial models, and case and ethnographic research. These diverse approaches offer a strong foundation on which the diverse complexities entailing financial sustainability are underscored but, again these seminal works expose gaps particularly within cross-sectional and, to an extent, temporal premise [30]. However, there is a dearth of information sharing in terms of analyzing the interconnections of the financial social, and environmental temporal behavior hence is seen as a potential area for development [31].

According to research, specialized subsidies, and sound revenue sources such as user charges and microfinancing have been found to improve financial viability [29]. Community-related factors such as community participation and stakeholder participation are also important. Consumer involvement enhances local stakeholding, which is crucial for the sustainability of the finances and the projects in times of difficulty [32]. External conditions are also important; replenishable resources should be effectively managed to withstand environmental risks, conservation of resources and provision of steady services must also be checked [33]. Further, they include governance structure, policy support, and capacity building which are also important at the institutional level. Greater control through effective governance structures and policies to support them can assist in improving financial planning and resource management thus leading to improvement in sustainability as noted by Bhandari and Grant in 2020 [27].

New ideas of smart water management systems or integration of renewable energy sources could open new ways to address the issue of financial sustainability [28]. Addressing global energy security challenges and achieving Sustainable Development Goals, focusing on a critical pathway for sustainable energy solutions is a role of sustainability science. [34] Furthermore, investing time in researching and identifying new and creative financial models and strategies of blended financing and public-

private partnership profiles could help to look for less reliance on traditional funding structures [31]. It has been noted that comparative cross-regional analysis is useful when it comes to identifying the similarities and differences in financial sustainability practices across different regions. Such comparison studies can provide a window into what has worked and what has not and hence provide a different perspective on the strategies that could be adopted [29]. Last but not least; longitudinal studies, where the effects of the projects and their influences on the financial sustainability can be captured over several years are required. These sorts of studies may help to achieve an enhanced understanding of factors related to early project conditions or subsequent interventions that determine sustained outcomes and stability [27].

II. Methodology

To obtain the maximum information for the systematic literature review, an elaborate search strategy was used. The searched electronic databases were PubMed, Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus. This was done by using the following keywords and search terms: “financial sustainability”, “community-managed water supply”, “developing countries”, “water supply projects” and “sustainable water management”. The terms were searched using the Boolean operators “AND” and “OR” so that the results could be narrowed and widened in the search.

Inclusion criteria for selecting studies were as follows: Concerning the original research questions the following database and filters were used: relevance to the financial sustainability of community-managed water supply projects in developing countries, publication year between 2000 and 2023, language, and both qualitative & Quantitative, Full-text availability. Studies outside the water supply intervention papers that discussed the technical aspects without any financial planning and management, and articles written in languages other than English. E-articles, unpublished reports, and these were excluded.

Several screening stages had to be completed for candidates to be chosen for an offer. First, the foundation was laid by evaluating the titles and abstracts of all identified articles, and filtering out irrelevant research studies using specific exclusion criteria. Articles that passed this initial filtering were then assessed more thoroughly through additional title and abstract reviews to determine their suitability for the final list. The selection process, including the number of records, records screened, records after the initial assessment, and records included in the review, was illustrated using a PRISMA flow diagram for systematic review and meta-analysis. The PRISMA flow diagram provides a visual representation of the study selection process, detailing the following steps: Database search for identification of records [47,342], and from other sources [1,208]; reviewed after duplicate [47,342]; titles and abstracts

[1,709] ; records excluded [1,208]; full-text eligibility assessment [501] and excluded [337]; qualitative synthesis [164] and quantitative synthesis meta-analysis [33].

The primary research revealed that the included studies varied in terms of study design, geographical location, and sample size. Key effective financial management practices identified from the studies included: a] a written accounting system, b] formal financial audits, and c] community participation in budget development. Common sources of funding were user fees, government grants, and development assistance, with successful projects often employing multiple methods to ensure a steady and reliable income. Several cost recovery strategies were highlighted, such as price differentiation and microcredit services, leading to a higher cost recovery ratio, which serves as an indicator of long-term sustainability. Factors like community involvement, governmental support, and a favorable policy environment were found to positively influence financial sustainability.

Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram

A standardized checklist was used to assess the methodological quality of the identified studies, evaluating the risk of bias, the rigor of the study design, and the credibility of the reported outcomes. The review also highlighted both positive and negative comparisons across various variables in the included studies. Similarities, such as community participation and reliance on multiple funding sources, were observed, alongside differences in financial management approaches, which varied according to the socio-economic contexts of their regions of origin.

Key recommendations for enhancing financial sustainability in community-managed water supply

projects include strengthening the capacity of the community in financial literacy and management, implementing transparent and accountable governance systems, and diversifying revenue sources. Policy suggestions emphasize the need for favorable policies, financial incentives, subsidies, and promoting public-private partnerships to mobilize additional resources. However, a limitation of this review is that the quality and sample size of the studies may impact the generalizability of the conclusions. Additionally, restricting the review to English-language databases and publications, while excluding grey literature, may have led to the omission of important information. Following PRISMA flow diagram represents the systematic study of this paper

III. Result and Discussion

The included studies of this systematic literature review varied concerning study type, participating country, and population size. The study designs included case studies, empirical research, and econometric approaches to the research problems investigated. The place of the studies was diverse with the samples collected from several developing countries across Asia, Africa, and Latin

America. It included quantitative and qualitative data samples involving small-size community-based projects to enormous national-level research studies avoiding the middle ground and providing a wider view of the financial sustainability of community-managed water supply projects inancial Management Practices

It was determined that effective financial management practices are crucial for the sustainability of community water supply programs. Such practices include financial accounting, periodic financial audits, and community participation in the preparation of financial budgets. For instance, the research done by [13] explained the relevance of these practices to improve accountability to ensure proper disbursement and usage of the funds.

Sources of Funding and Revenue Generation

The studies revealed that diverse revenue generation sources are essential for the sustainability of these projects. Projects rely on a combination of funding sources, including user fees, government subsidies, and international donations, to maintain consistent cash flow and financial stability. For instance, Whittington et al [29] focused on adopting diversified funding mechanisms, as they provide greater financial sustainability to water supply projects.

Table 1. Top 10 Literature

Author[s]	Year	Title	Journal/ Publisher	Key Themes	Key Findings
Bhandari & Grant	2020	Financial sustainability of community-managed water supply projects: A case study analysis	Journal of Water Resource Management	Financial sustainability, community management	The case study revealed challenges in long-term financial sustainability and suggested cost-recovery mechanisms.
Harvey & Reed	2007	Community-managed water supplies in Africa: Sustainable or dispensable?	Community Development Journal	Community management, sustainability, Africa	Highlighted mixed outcomes of community-managed systems in Africa and emphasized the need for technical support and capacity building.
Gleick, P. H.	2014	Water, drought, climate change, and conflict in Syria	Weather, Climate, and Society	Climate change, water management, conflict	Linked the collapse of community-managed water systems in Syria to drought and climate-induced conflict.
Kleemeier, E.	2000	The impact of participation on sustainability: An analysis of the Malawi Rural Piped Scheme Program	World Development	Community participation, sustainability	Demonstrated that greater community participation improves the sustainability of rural water schemes.

Montgomery, Bartram, & Elimelech	2009	Increasing functional sustainability of water and sanitation supplies in rural sub-Saharan Africa	Environmental Engineering Science	Sustainability, rural water systems, Sub-Saharan Africa	Found that improving system management and providing local ownership are essential for sustainability in rural water projects.
Schouten & Moriarty	2003	Community Water, Community Management: From System to Service in Rural Areas	ITDG Publishing	Community water management, rural areas	Analyzed transition from system-based to service-oriented approaches, stressing long-term sustainability in rural water management.
Poudel, D.	2019	Smart water management systems: Emerging trends and financial sustainability	International Journal of Water Resources Development	Smart water management, sustainability	Explored emerging trends in water management systems and recommended innovations for financial sustainability.
Kariuki & Schwartz	2005	Small-scale private service providers of water supply and electricity: A review of incidence, structure, pricing, and operating characteristics	World Bank Policy Research Working Paper	Private providers, water supply, pricing	Investigated the role of small-scale private water providers in improving financial sustainability in underserved areas.
Whittington, Davis, & McClelland	1998	Implementing a demand-driven approach to community water supply planning: A case study of Lugazi, Uganda	Water International	Demand-driven approach, community water supply, Uganda	Found that a demand-driven approach improved community ownership and financial viability of water supply projects.
Majale, M.	2002	Livelihoods approaches compared: A brief comparison of the livelihoods approaches of DFID, CARE, Oxfam, and UNDP	ResearchGate	Livelihoods, community development, water supply	Compared various livelihoods approaches to water projects, highlighting their financial sustainability in relation to community involvement and external support.

111. 1. Cost Recovery Mechanisms

Research suggests different cost recovery mechanisms, including tiered pricing and microfinancing, can contribute to project sustainability. It was observed that projects with higher cost recovery rates shown greater long-term success. Majale [2002] [20] and Bhandari & Grant [2015] [15] highlight the critical need for implementing effective cost-recovery strategies to ensure

the financial sustainability of water supply systems by covering essential operational and maintenance costs.

Factors Affecting Financial Sustainability

The research identified several key factors influencing the financial sustainability of community-managed water supply projects, including community participation, government support, and strong policy frameworks. Community participation, in particular, emerged as a

critical element for maintaining financial health by fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility among community members [32]. Additionally, supportive government policies and frameworks are essential for resource allocation and facilitation of better financial planning. [35].

111. 2 Quality Assessment Methodological Quality of Included Studies

The quality of the methodological approach used in the Identified studies was the next criterion checked using an established checklist. This evaluation involved a careful review of several aspects, including the robustness of the study designs, the clarity and transparency of the methods used, and the overall reliability of the results. The studies that included well-laid-down methodology and adequate data analyses were of higher quality.

111. 3 Risk of Bias Assessment

The assessment of bias involved an examination of potential biases in the study designs and methodologies. This included an evaluation of aspects such as sample selection, data collection methods, and the divisions for outcome measurement. Some studies were found to have a low risk of bias due to their robust design, while others displayed potential biases related to sample selection and data collection procedures [31].

The included studies presented a combination of similarities and differences in their findings and conclusions regarding the financial sustainability of community-managed water supply projects. However, a recurring theme across most studies was the highlighted importance of community participation in promoting financial sustainability. Research by [35] Majale [2002] and Harvey & Reed [2007] [13] highlighted that community involvement fosters the ownership and accountability necessary for effective project management and financial health. However, variations were noted in the financial models and approaches used in different areas. For example, some studies described successful strategies such as tiered pricing mechanisms and microfinance solutions [27] [Bhandari & Grant, 2020], while others addressed challenges in setting appropriate user charges that balance sustainability with affordability for target clients [24]. This underscores the importance of adopting context-sensitive financial approaches tailored to the unique socio-economic conditions of each community. Several factors were found to influence the micro-financial feasibility of community-led water supply projects. Key aspects decisive to financial sustainability included diversified funding sources and stable revenue streams. The study suggests that projects utilizing a diverse range of revenue sources, such as user fees, government subsidies, and international aid, had a higher probability of achieving long-term financial sustainability.

[13] [29]. Furthermore, social factors like local engagement, community relations, and stakeholder management significantly influenced successful project outcomes. Active community involvement supported a sense of ownership and accountability, which proved beneficial for both financial and long-term sustainability [36]. Regarding community sustainability, aspects like resource quality and accessibility were essential for preventing resource depletion and promoting environmental stability during service delivery [30]. Furthermore, governance structures and policies that supported the development of institutional capacity also contributed to improved financial planning and resource management, further enhancing overall sustainability [27].

To improve the financial sustainability of community-managed water supply projects, several strategies could be employed as raising community awareness about financial management, implementing sound financial practices, establishing effective governance mechanisms, and diversifying income sources. Providing financial management and literacy training to community members can significantly address shortcomings in budgeting, accounting, and resource allocation. This, in turn, fosters good financial practices and bolsters financial sustainability [13].

The efficient and transparent management of funds and resources, coupled with adequate oversight and control, is of utmost importance [14]. Expanding income streams by utilizing various sources, such as user fees, microfinancing, and government subsidies, helps reduce dependency on a single revenue stream and enhances financial stability [29]. Furthermore, actively involving the community in the decision-making process, especially concerning water supply projects, is vital for enhancing management practices and ensuring long-term sustainability [36].

Policies aimed at fostering financial sustainability should prioritize the creation of a supportive legal and regulatory environment, offer grant-based incentives and subsidies, and encourage collaborations between communities, public entities, and other stakeholders. It's essential to establish well-funded policies that specifically support community assets involved in water supply projects, ensuring a favorable legal framework for their successful operation [27]. Providing financial incentives and support for community-managed projects, both in the form of initial investments and ongoing operational expenses, can significantly contribute to their long-term sustainability [28]. Collaborations between the public and private sectors can bring in additional resources and technical expertise, potentially enhancing the financial viability of water supply projects [31].

Several key considerations were identified from the appraisal of the included studies and the review process itself. The papers included in the present review are moderate in their quality as some of them can be potentially biased regarding the representative samples,

and the techniques used to gather the information. Furthermore, due to the variability of the studies, it was hard to compare the results across diverse geographical areas. Several sources that have not published their studies in the English language or journals were excluded during this process of review hence they could have provided other perspectives. Moreover, using available databases and searched terms might have led to the omission of relevant studies which was not included in the searched databases.

It brought the centrality of financial sustainability in the communities responsible for the water supply improvement projects. On sustainability, the factors that were found included the proper management of funds, more than one source of funds, and the participation of the community and support of government policies. These findings pointed to the need to adopt and implement financial solutions tailored to the socio-economic environment of the targeted communities. Further research should aim at discovering new opportunities for financing water infrastructure and technologies together with other options for the application of advanced technologies in water management, namely Smart Water Management Systems, and Renewable Energy System Integration [37]. Moreover, it requires longitudinal analysis to apprehend the temporal changes in financial sustainability and how the characteristics of the initial projects influence the success and stability of projects in the organization [35]. Cross-regional comparative studies may help to develop more general ideas of the efficient strategies and the peculiarities of the contexts of financial sustainability activities

IV. Conclusion and Recommendations

The systematic literature review provides evidence that financial sustainability is a key factor affecting community-managed water supply projects in developing nations. Key findings include identification of the major factors that are vital in the sustainability of the projects such as accountability in fund sourcing and management, periodic financial audits, and the involvement of the community within the budgeting process. It was ascertained that revenue diversification which includes user fees, government subsidies, and international aid plays critical in revenue sustainability. A variety of plausible cost recovery tools, including differentiated pricing strategies as well as microfinancing schemes helped to meet the long-run financial requirements of water supply systems. Furthermore, in the outlined studies, the issues of participation to ensure ownership and accountability at the community level, good governance, and favourable government policies to support improved planning and management of funds and other resources were highlighted.

Future Research Directions Identified Gaps in the Current Literature

The review identified the following research gaps in the existing literature on the operations, financial sustainability, and financing of community-managed water supply projects. The studies on project development over extended timelines are crucial for seeing the key factors of financial sustainability over a long period. Furthermore, there is a lack of comparative research between regions that could demonstrate strengths and weaknesses in different geographical and socio-economic environments, which could be valuable for practitioners. The review of the literature also reveals the absence of a historical perspective in research and a lack of integration of financial, social, and environmental factors which shows a need for more comprehensive and temporally based research in this area.

Suggested Areas for Future Research

Future research should be directed toward analyzing new sources of funding and technological advancements in the water sector. For instance, smart water management systems and renewable energy sources could be a fresh model for increasing the financial viability of water supply projects. There is a need for follow-up studies to assess the effects of initial project characteristics and implemented changes on the sustenance of success. Achieving the above would deepen the understanding of the factors that influence the long-term sustainability of water supply systems. Furthermore, efforts should be made to make cross-regional comparisons to compare the various contexts and similarities in the practices for sustainable finance. Comparative analyses would be useful to compare the different models and to form a base to construct specific programs according to the scenario. Lastly, future studies should explore how sustainable financial models, strategic partnerships, and financial structures like blended financing can effectively support community-managed water supply projects.

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